

Efficiency in the American Option Market: a study of Martingales with a Marxian model for wages

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Abstract

The American Option Market is not defined importantly as it should be, the pledge holders would wait for given the stopping time uncertainty is sufficient, the stopping time of the American Option under some circumstances is really hard to model, we have supposed wages are indeed responsible for prices without knocking on the doors of dead people, Marx theory of value is honourable.

The American Option Market has some theoretical correlation with risk in the Stock Market, we had identified this correlation while hedging the value of Options using wages under a socialist framework, the Options are regarded as martingales if the Market is efficient, however this operational question lies in making an investigation about where American style Options behave like Martingales under a Marxist framework, our model gets its legitimacy from the theory of value which was presented by Marx fellows and himself.

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1 Introduction

The American Option Market is not easy to model whatsoever, the stopping time is random which means that the payoff is difficult to model in a statistical way.

This article first of all is an honouring to Karl Marx by supposing that wages framework is Marxian, the fact prices depend only on wages as the Marxian theory of value states is defining the behavior of price changes, the function g has to be null in our model so that we would give reason to Marx and his fellows.

Options are volatile and very sensitive to risk in the Stock Market (volatility), we supposed volatility is fractional for statistical reasons which is also an euphoric hypothesis, income as well might be responsible for American Options variations, we then identified the terms of our correlation using a system, which is innovative because besides the tree that we built we add another equation to catch Options change.

Afterward we investigated in the efficiency of American Options Market using randomness between the tree we built and the fact the payoff of such a claim has not been caught.

Ilegbinosa, Anthony. (2012) has discussed the theory of value stemming from Karl Marx theory and had given a light explanation for this finding, first of all we presented a model for wages which is fully inspired from marxism and socialism, workers are not given a lot of choice and are always paid off under what they indeed deserve which makes the function s more hypothetical under our model which takes its legitimacy from this paper.

Afterward we had presented a model for prices which depend fully on wages under a fair capitalist faux-system, socialists are always encouraging subsidies from the state, it is indeed not very useful to make prices depending only on salaries, our model is a clear result of the theory of values that Marx had developed during the nineteenth century: prices depend only on wages in a fair state which makes the function g very likely to depend on other factors which we did not assume in our knowledge, what matters for us is the fact g is null under a free-enterprise socialism-oriented system, the vocation of this article is presenting a form of state by using statistics and operational economics proposing an original model which is first of all legitimate and doesn't *à priori* need application, the correctness of our model lies in the novelty and the divinity of Sir Karl Marx may God blesses him in my opinion.

Afterward, under our marxist model we have been interested in the American Option Market for which a study of the efficiency was presented briefly after building a correlation between risk in the Stock Market and the premium of an American Option, when Options or American Options are presented as martingales, our model contains some euphoric hypothesis that we mustn't justify *à priori* unless we can imagine more for our blessings, the initial conditions in differential equations are indeed given by the majesty of intuition or at least past recommendations, we have also set off some hypothesis using our deep intuition, the research question lies in finding out where the American Option Market finds evidence to be efficient or a martingale under our model and non extended hypothesis that we didn't have the time to remake for twice.

Arun Chockalingam and Kumar Muthuraman (2011) have been concerned by the pricing of American Options using a stochastic volatility, our article deals arguably with a fractal volatility and presented a model for pricing American Option using their correlation with income (wages) and risk in the stock market (volatility), this article shows how likely the premium of an American Option can depend on stochastic volatility.

2 Model

Under the criticism of Karl Marx in *Das Kapital* his well-known book the capitalist system isn't fair with workers, we can write the current state of wages as

$$w_t^* = w_t + s_t$$

Where s_t is the surplus value defined by Marx which comes as a profit at the cost of the labour force, the real wage includes such a compromise under a rational point of view.

Hypothesis1: We should consider that

$$E^{H_1}[s_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] = 0$$

with H called a probability of growth, the shape of $(H_i)_{i \geq 0}$ would be the following, we would later on explain why its form looks like this

$$\frac{dH_i}{dH_{i+1}} = \frac{p_{t+i+1}}{E^{H_i}[p_{t+i}/\mathcal{F}_{t+i-1}]}$$

Hypothesis2: We would consider that under a Marxian framework the volatility of wages δ is almost constant because none would be enriched abruptly and the level of wages is stable and constant over two consecutive periods

$$w_{t+1} = aw_t + \delta\epsilon_t$$

Where $a \approx 1$

According to Karl Marx prices depend only on the labour time which means, that labour is the source of all value, we would try to enforce this assumption to justify the *first écriture* of the probability H , we write the following and keep in mind that it is only euphoric that we turn our attention to the novelty of socialism further

$$p_t = \beta w_t + g(t)$$

With $\beta > 0$

The expectation of g under the probability of growth H defined earlier on is null under a Marxian framework because there is nothing the price should depend on unless workers are foolish, it's fair indeed, which means in my opinion that Marx had shed off some morality on capitalism to be honest, let's write the following

$$E^{H_1}[g(t+1)/\mathcal{F}_t] = E^{H_1}[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] - \beta w_t^* + \beta s_t$$

In a Marxian framework

$$E^{H_1}[g(t+1)/\mathcal{F}_t] = 0$$

Which means

$$w_t^* = \frac{1}{\beta} E^{H_1}[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] + s_t$$

Which means

$$E^{H_1}[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] = \beta w_t$$

If we suppose that whenever companies can stand on time α their futures expectations about g are null, we would find out this correlation between prices which comes to justify why we baptize H a probability of growth, it is defined upon the growth of the real price g .

$$E^{H_1}[p_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] = E^{H_0}[p_t/\mathcal{F}_{t-1}]$$

Under such a probability H_1 we would evaluate consumption, companies should decrease their consumption in the favour of the working class under a Marxian situation, let's write it down in those terms

$$E^{H_1}[C_{t+1}/\mathcal{F}_t] = \xi C_t$$

With $\xi < 1$ Which gives

$$E^{H_0}[p_t/\mathcal{F}_{t-1}] = \frac{\xi C_t}{LC_{t+1}}$$

With $L = \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-t(\nu - t\sigma))dt$; $\nu = a\beta w_t$ and $\sigma = \beta\delta$

The Figarch model is specified as mean reverting equation using the following formula as a starting point:

$$\Phi(L)(1-L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Psi(L)g(z_{t-1})$$

Where ω is the mean variance and $\Phi(L)$ and $\Psi(L)$ are polynomials in the lag operator, $\Phi(L) = (1 - \Phi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Phi_p L)$ and $\Psi(L) = (1 - \Psi_1 L) \times \dots (1 - \Psi_p L)$ and $(1-L)^d$ is the fractional difference operator defined by its binomial expansion:

$$(1-L)^d = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(i-d)}{\Gamma(-d)\Gamma(i+1)} L^i$$

The function g above is allowed to include the effect past returns has on the current volatility and has the following form:

$$g(z_t) = \theta z_t + \gamma(|z_t| - E|z_t|)$$

where $z_t = \frac{\epsilon_t}{\sigma_t}$ is the normalized innovation

we take into consideration the character volatility always shows as a mean reverting function tending to converge to a constant value and we should define it again as the following:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega)$$

It is then convenient to write the FIGARCH(1,d,1) model as:

$$h_t = (1 - L)^d(\ln\sigma_t^2 - \omega) = \Phi_1 h_{t-1} + g(z_{t-1}) + \Psi_1 g(z_{t-2})$$

3 Pricing of Futures and Options under a Marxian system (Socialist)

Our vocation is to find a suitable price for Options under the risk neutral measure, for this reason we would present the martingale measure in another way to obtain a form for the pricing of classical Options, for that aim the tool we might use for instance is the Futures price

$$\begin{aligned} F(t, T) &= E^{\mathcal{Q}^*}[p_T / \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= a^n \beta w_t \\ &= a^n E^{H_1}[p_{t+1} / \mathcal{F}_t] \end{aligned}$$

The risk neutral measure is thus represented *ainsi*

$$\frac{dH_1}{dQ^*} = \frac{p_T}{a^n E^{H_1}[p_{t+1} / \mathcal{F}_t]}$$

The price of a Vanilla Option under the risk neutral measure should be

$$C_t = E[(p_T - K)^+ \exp(-r(T - t)) / \mathcal{F}_t]$$

Whereas

$$E[p_T \mathbb{1}_{p_T \geq K} / \mathcal{F}_t] = a^n E^{H_1}[p_{t+1} / \mathcal{F}_t] Q^*(a^n \beta w_t + \sum_{i=1}^n a^i \delta \beta \epsilon_{T-i} \geq K)$$

3.1 A model for pricing American Options

Income is very crucial in apprehending the theory around quantitative finance, the correlation between the level of income and American Options value can be the case of a crucial study, we present in the following a model that incorporates the correlation between income and American Options

$$\mathcal{A}_t = A(t, T)w_t + B(t, T)h_t$$

Where T is the maturity of the American Option if we presume the shareholder is going to hold it truly and not exercise it. Besides the correlation between the level of income or arguably wages and American Options premium, the volatility of the Stock Market has in fact an effect on American Options.

On the other hand, the price of an American Option is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_t &= E[A_\tau \exp(-r(\tau - t)) / \mathcal{F}_t] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n P(f = i) B(t + i, T) \Phi^i \exp(-ri) h_t + \sum_{i=1}^n P(f = i) A(t + i, T) E[w_{t+i} / \mathcal{F}_t] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where $\tau = \sup_{t \leq u \leq T} (S_u)$ and $\tau = t + f$

Which means

$$B(t, T) = \sum_{i=1}^n P(f = i) B(t + i, T) \Phi^i \exp(-ri)$$

The psychology of the shareholders matters for us, at any time t the holder of an American Options under some specific expectations about welfare that we gather in the probability space $(\Omega, H, \mathcal{F}_t)$, the holder of such a contract has some hope about the coming instant to be the right time for exercise which would lead us to write

$$\mathcal{A}_t = E^H[\exp(-r)\mathcal{A}_{t+1} / \mathcal{F}_t]$$

For every $t \leq T - 1$

Which means

$$\begin{aligned} B(t, T) &= B(t + i, T) \Phi^i \exp(-ri) \quad \forall i \geq 1 \\ A(t + i, T) &= \frac{\exp(ir) \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} w_{t+j} A(t, T)}{\prod_{j=1}^i E[w_{t+j} / \mathcal{F}_t]} \end{aligned}$$

Which means using (1)

$$A(t+i, T) = A(t, T) \exp(ir) \prod_{j=0}^{i-1} \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\prod_{l=0}^{k-1} w_{t+j+l}}{\prod_{l=1}^k E[w_{t+j+l} / \mathcal{F}_t]}}{\prod_{j=1}^i E[w_{t+j} / \mathcal{F}_t]}$$

4 Methodology and calibration

We sought to define the American Option Market in those conditions:

First of all the price relies all in wages, in a socialist climate or at least a Marxian framework we sought to define prices with respect to all the value they are embedding, in this socialist situation the function g which might depend on other factors which might be responsible for price change has to be null if Karl Marx and his fellows are true about the theory of value, it is also a classical fabulous point of view.

Afterward we aim to build a correlation between American Options and income, volatility or arguably the risk in the Stock Market affects the price of an Option. Afterward let's enforce the following hypothesis:

$$E^H[\mathcal{A}_\tau/\mathcal{F}_{t-n}] = \mathcal{A}_{t+1-n}f(t-n, T)$$

With $f(t-n, T) = 1$ and τ is the Stopping time for the exercise of the American Option price, this hypothesis is functional, we suppose that

$$\begin{aligned} E^H[\mathcal{A}_\tau/\mathcal{F}_t] &= \mathcal{A}_{t+1}f(t, T) \\ E[\mathcal{A}_\tau/\mathcal{F}_t] &= E[\mathcal{A}_\tau/\mathcal{F}_{t-1}] \end{aligned}$$

Which means that following the concept of the psychological price that we had defined earlier on the holder of the American Option has some expectations about the payoff of the American Option which is random, we sought to represent this randomness using the \mathcal{F}_t adapted process $f(t, T)$.

With respect to the definition we had given to the probability above H that was a psychological reaction from the holder of the American Option \mathcal{A}_t , the last stochastic equilibrium would translate into

$$E[\mathcal{A}_\tau \frac{\mathcal{A}_t}{\mathcal{A}_{t+1}}/\mathcal{F}_t] \exp(r) = \mathcal{A}_{t+1}f(t, T)$$

Whereas

$$E[\mathcal{A}_\tau \frac{\mathcal{A}_t}{\mathcal{A}_{t+1}}/\mathcal{F}_t] = E[\mathcal{A}_\tau \frac{\mathcal{A}_t}{E^H[\mathcal{A}_\tau/\mathcal{F}_t]}f(t, T)/\mathcal{F}_t]$$

The above hypothesis relaxes that $E[\mathcal{A}_\tau/\mathcal{F}_t] = E[\mathcal{A}_\tau/\mathcal{F}_{t-1}]$ which means that the expectation of the American Options holders don't change regarding how likely the payoff would take place, besides our hypothesis that under the probability H the exercise time is everytime regarded as the coming instant, the payoff in itself doesn't change in the eyes of holders, any model has rigorous hypothesis, the latter is indeed very restricting however it has shown alike how this kind of Options is not easy to implement

theoretically. Afterward we have the following

$$\begin{aligned}
E[\mathcal{A}_\tau \frac{\mathcal{A}_t}{\mathcal{A}_{t+1}} / \mathcal{F}_t] &= E[\mathcal{A}_\tau \frac{f(t, T)}{f(t-1, T)} / \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= \frac{1}{f(t-1, T)} E[E[\mathcal{A}_\tau f(t, T) / \mathcal{F}_t] / \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&= E[\mathcal{A}_{t+1} f(t, T)^2 / \mathcal{F}_t]
\end{aligned}$$

Which means

$$f(t, T) = \frac{\mathcal{A}_{t+1} \exp(-r)}{E[\mathcal{A}_{t+1} / \mathcal{F}_t]} f(t-1, T)$$

We should be investigating in the efficiency of American Options Markets using an appropriate space $S(\mathcal{R})$, we would then enforce $\mathcal{A}_{t+1} f(t, T) = \mathcal{A}_t$ and get then

$$f(t-n, T) \exp(-nr) \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{\mathcal{A}_{t+1-i}}{E[\mathcal{A}_{t+1-i} / \mathcal{F}_t]} = \mathcal{A}_t$$

Which gives symmetrically

$$\exp(-nr) \prod_{i=0, i \neq 1}^{n-1} \frac{\mathcal{A}_{t+1-i}}{E[\mathcal{A}_{t+1-i} / \mathcal{F}_t]} \frac{1}{E[\mathcal{A}_t / \mathcal{F}_t]} = 1$$

It's not convenient to give the optimal path of volatility that allows the American Option Market to be efficient, tis the following

$$\exp(-nr) \prod_{i=0, i \neq 1}^{n-1} \frac{\mathcal{A}_{t+1-i}}{E[\mathcal{A}_{t+1-i} / \mathcal{F}_t]} = A(t, t)w_t + B(t, T)h_t$$

Conclusion: After making more incentives for what an American Option might look like, we give evidence about the whereabouts of efficiency in the American Option Market under our model.

The theory we developed can be applicable to a wide range of indexes that follow a FIGARCH process, we did not pursue this road as the best finding of our manuscript is its theoretical evidence which is strong and inspirational.

declarations:

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